

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ABOUT THE STUDY OF TURKISH LANGUAGES IN FRANCE

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Abstract

The study of the Turkish language and research on the history, civilization and institutions of the Turkish and Ottoman worlds is a tradition that can be traced back to the sixteenth century, when relations were established between the French kingdom and the Ottoman empire; The promotion of the Turkic world in the perspectives of the alliance was stimulated by two innovations of great importance: the establishment of the College Royal (later the College de France), where Turkish and Arabic languages were taught, and the collection of Ottoman manuscripts and texts in the Bibliotheque Royale, later the Bibliotheque Nationale.

Keywords: Turkish language, research, France, Ottoman, Bibliotheque Royale.

The opening of the French Embassy in Istanbul and the establishment of consulates in the main ports of the Ottoman Empire led to the establishment of closer relations with the Turkish world, especially the School of Oriental Languages, which was the basis of the School of Oriental Languages (now the National Institute of Eastern Languages and Civilizations) established in Paris in 1795. The Youth Language School, which was established in 1669 within the Istanbul Embassy, resulted in the training of a significant number of translators. From the end of the seventeenth century, several translators were closely interested in the language, literature, history and civilization of the Ottoman Empire, becoming, we can say, the first French orientalist (East experts). The names Antoine Galland and Petis de la Croix are very well-known and their historical role should be noted. Since these translators were the compilers of the manuscripts, many Turkish books and documents, not all of which have been examined yet, are collected in the National Library. From then on, knowledge about the Turkish world would gradually increase, and only in the nineteenth century would scientific research on Orientalism and Turkism really begin. Until the beginning of the twentieth century, orientalist were versatile.

They are experts on the Turkish world and the Arab world - and even the Iranian world - that were integrated into the Ottoman state. The coexistence of languages and civilizations necessitates this versatility. If this feature is not taken into consideration, these realms cannot be understood as real. But these orientalist also have a very scientific side; That is, the field of his research covers language, literature, philology, religion and history; Since special studies were not yet developed, the orientalist of this period could be considered encyclopedists [1-2].

They resulted in the proliferation and deepening of research on Oriental and especially Turkic studies in various fields, the specialization of their teaching, and especially the development of research that adopted the methods and lenses of other human sciences. After the Second World War, the death of Paul Pelliot in 1945 and the retirement of Jean Deny in 1949 led to the emergence of a new generation of Turkologists. For a long time, the only place where the Turkish language was taught in France was the School of Oriental Languages;

Occasionally, Turkish language courses were also given at the College in France until the end of the nineteenth century. In 1950, the Department of Turkish History and Philology Studies was established within the Ecole Pratique des Hautes Etudes in Paris, in the department of historical and philological sciences; Louis Bazin was appointed as the responsible manager of this department. Beyond this position, Louis Bazin is currently a professor of Turkish at the National Institute of Eastern Languages and Civilizations. In 1996, the Department of Turkish Language and Civilization was established at the Aix en Provence Faculty of Letters (a part of the current university with Provence/Aix Marse) and its management was given to me; In 1962, a similar chair was established at the University of Strasbourg, and first Rene Giraud and then Irene Melikoff were appointed to its management. The teaching programs in these institutions have different characteristics of their own: Teaching at the National Institute of Eastern Languages is long for the living Turkish in Turkey; Teaching at the Ecole des Hautes Etudes deals with ancient and medieval philology, studying subjects such as Mongolian and Yenisei Epigraphy, Runiform and Uyghur texts; The education in Strasbourg includes, on the one hand, the current Turkish language, and on the other hand, the legend, epic and religious literature of Anatolia in the Middle Ages and the examination of the different sects of the current Anatolian religious associations. In Aix en Provence, teaching is carried out on the contemporary Turkish language and especially on the history and civilization of the Ottoman state. For several years, Alexandre Bennigsen has been giving lectures on "Turkish Nations in the Soviet Union" at the School of Higher Studies in Social Sciences; Nicoara Beldiceanu also lectures on paleography and pre-Ottoman history [3-4].

Research teams have been established around these higher education centers with the financial and material assistance of the Universities and the Center National de la Recherche Scientifique, and many other research teams continue their work.

Louis Bazin, the director of one of the Paris research teams, directed and conducted research on the pre-Islamic Turkic world of High Asia and Central Asia and Turkish inscriptions. He presents the results of these studies in his doctoral thesis titled "Ancient and

Medieval Turkish Calendars", which constitutes the basis for the science of the pre-Islamic Turkish world; While historical thoughts gain the necessary explanations, clear date determinations of inscriptional texts are made. Another part of Bazin's work concerns studies in historical and comparative linguistics: the history of the dictionary, research on the spoken languages of the Turkic group, etc. In this field, Jacqueline Baraji's book "Les relations Spatiels en turc Contemporain Etude Smantique" should also be mentioned. As for James Hamilton, he specialized in the study of Uyghur texts, regularly publishing the Toueng Hang documents formerly brought by Paul Pelliot. He was able to add knowledge of the Chinese language to his knowledge of ancient Turkic languages and carry out a deep critical analysis of these texts. The philological and linguistic studies on the Kyrgyz language by Slavic languages expert and Turkologist Guy Imart led to the emergence of his doctoral thesis. As for Remy Dor, he studies the unique traditions of the Afghan Kyrgyz in the Pamirs. Jean Paul Roux, who added complementary research on Seljuk sculpture to his research on the religious traditions of Central Asian and then Anatolian Turkish Nations, provides important works. Apart from his studies on the relations of the Ottoman Campaign, Jean – Louis Bacqu - Grammont studied and published Chagatai texts and was interested in Selim I's campaigns in Egypt and Syria. In another field, the works of Pertev Naili Boratav, a great expert on Turkish folklore and oral literature, Michle Nicolas's studies on Turkish traditions, his studies on fish and fishing in Turkey, Altan Gökalp's ethno-sociological studies on the Anatolian Chepni. By the way, it should be reminded [5-6].

Irene Melikoff, who is interested in Seljuk and pre-Ottoman Medieval Turkish literature at the University of Strasbourg, studies Alevi circles in Anatolia in the Middle Ages and Modern Times. Jacques Thobie, who has written a major thesis entitled "Interet et Imperialisme Français dans l'Empire Ottoman 1895-1914 - French interests and imperialism in the Ottoman empire) and specializes in the economic history of the last years of the Ottoman empire, manages a group of researchers related to these issues at the University of Reunes. Groupe de Recherches et d'Etudes sur le proche orient was established at the University of Aix en Provence, under its management. The history of the Arab provinces of the Ottoman Empire (mainly Egypt and Syria), Muslim cities during the Ottoman period (Cairo, Damascus, Haleb, Tunisia, Algeria), relations between North Africa and the Near East from the sixteenth to the nineteenth centuries, provincial and municipal institutions, epidemics in the Eastern Mediterranean in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries; Turkish inscriptions (Cairo, Damascus), and then the architecture of palaces and houses in Tunisia and Cairo are the research areas of this team. G. R. E. P. O. with his patronage, four volumes (belonging to the Mamluk and Ottoman periods) were published about the palaces and houses in Cairo. A synthesis volume, the history of the city of Cairo during the Mamluk era, was also published as a book this year; in a few weeks, the second volume - the Ottoman era - will be released. Other books were published. The "Egyptian letters of John

Ninet", the "Algerians and Tunisians in the Ottoman Empire from 1848 to 1914", the "City of Meliopolis" and the communiqués of a Colloque on Egypt in the nineteenth century were also published. An examination of the Turkological studies in France reveals the following important lines. The pre-Islamic Turkish world, the history of the Ottoman Empire from the fourteenth century to the eighteenth century, oral literature, religious literature. Of course, work in these areas will continue. Louis Bazin and his team's program includes the study of pre-Islamic Turkish texts from a linguistic and historical point of view; on the other hand, ethnolinguistic and social science research of the contemporary Turkish world is also included in the scope of this program [7-8].

In Paris, research on Seljuk and pre-Ottoman history is also carried out by Claude Cahen and Nicoara and Ir&le Beldiceanu. The social, administrative, economic and cultural aspects of this period created opportunities for intelligent studies, and a thesis about Cem Sultan, which shed light on the relations between the Ottoman Empire and the Western States in the last decade of the fifteenth century, was defended by a young Turkologist, Nicolas Cetni. Turkish and Iranian relations during the time of Selim I and Shah Ismail in the sixteenth century were the subject of the works of Jean-Louis Bacque Grammont. His thesis illuminates the political and religious characteristics of these relations. Christiane Villain Gandom examines Venetian documents from the Ottoman Empire in the sixteenth century, and Michel Lesure published a book based on documents on the battle of Lepanto.

The research conducted by another team, Alexandre Bennigsen and Clintal Lemerrier Quelquejay, has two directions: one is the study of the Danubian provinces of the Ottoman Empire in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, with the work of Gilles Veinstein and Mihnea Berindei; The other is the history of the Turkish nations that have remained within the geographical borders of the current Soviet Union since the sixteenth century.

More recently, Paul Dumont's research on the political and social life of the Ottoman state at the end of the nineteenth century and the beginning of the twentieth century should be reported, as well as François Georgeon's research on Turkish nationalist movements of the same time (especially his thesis on Yusuf Akçura) [8-9].

Studies on the geography of the Turkish world are directed by Xavier de Planhol. At the University of Nancy, Marcel Bazin conducts research on the same subject.

Under the influence of French Turkologists, young Tunisian and Algerian researchers began to study the Arab and Turkish archives belonging to the Ottoman period in their home countries. The first results aroused hope. Now we can wait for documents that bring a new light that can illuminate the history of a dark era. July i 98o of the second International congress on the social and economic history of the Ottoman Empire and Turkey convened in Strasbourg and I would like to note by the way that the congress Decrees are in print. We cannot pass by without mentioning the

place and role of the journal *Turcica*, published by the Association pour le Développement des Etudes Turques, founded by French Turkologists, and the Institute of Turkish Studies of the University of Strasbourg. Irne Melikoff occupies an enviable place among Turkish and Oriental publications thanks to the efforts of Jean-Louis Bacque Grammont and Paul Dumont; this magazine, open to Turkologists of all nations, publishes one volume every year, sometimes two volumes; the fourteenth volume (1982) is the most recent Dec. The seventh volume (1975) contains an almost complete bibliography of the works of French living Turkologists; a list of studies of Turkologists of other countries has been made in the following volumes. In the field of publishing, the publication of many Turkology books was supported by the collections of the Istanbul French Institute; in particular, French Turkologists who had close and friendly relations with Professor Ömer Lütfi Barkan published a book in his memory in 1980.

In France, Publications Orientalistes de France, Publications Universitaires de Lille Association Pour la Diffusion de la Pensée Française and other publishing houses have published many books written by French Turkologists many times with the help of the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique. In 1981, on the occasion of the centenary of the birth of the founder of the new Turkey in Ankara, French Turkologists also participated in a Franco-Turkish panel discussion on relations between France and Turkey during the reign of Mustafa Kemal Atatürk. The communiqués of this panel were published in the collection Cahiers de *Turcica* (*Turcica* notebooks).

Conclusions

The presented reports and projects show the vitality of French studies and research belonging to the Turkish and Ottoman realms. Research teams and researchers who receive significant support from universities and the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique receive both financial and financial assistance from these institutions, opportunities are provided for their work, teaching staffs are opened. In short, we can think that Turkology teaching and research in France has a healthy structure, that good days are waiting for it, and that it will contribute to the development of Turkish studies internationally, as it used to be. Thus, Pavet de Courteille, Barbier de Munard Paul Pelliot, especially modern Turkologists who are indebted to Jean Deny's scientific contributions will be able to continue their works; also, I respectfully commemorate the memory of Jean Deny, to whom the whole world of Turkology, which can be proud of its new generation, owes.

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